

Assertiveness: A Concept Analysis in Nursing

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ABSTRACT

Assertiveness is a critical communication skill in nursing, influencing patient care, teamwork, and professional advocacy. This concept analysis explores assertiveness within the nursing profession using Walker and Avant's eight-step method. The defining attributes of assertiveness include confidence, respect, self-expression, and boundary-setting. Antecedents such as self-awareness, professional training, and workplace culture play a significant role in developing assertive behaviors, while consequences include improved nurse-patient relationships, reduced workplace stress, and enhanced interdisciplinary collaboration. The analysis differentiates assertiveness from related concepts such as aggression, passivity, and submissiveness. Model, borderline, and contrary cases illustrate its practical application in nursing settings. By clarifying the meaning and significance of assertiveness, this study provides a foundation for nursing education and practice, emphasizing the need for assertiveness training to foster effective communication and leadership in healthcare.

Keywords: Assertiveness, Concept Analysis, Nursing, Communication, Professionalism, Leadership.

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INTRODUCTION

Assertiveness is an adaptive communication style in which individuals express their feelings and needs directly while maintaining respect for others, known as assertiveness. It may be further defined by the absence of assertiveness which may result in other distorted ways of behaving, such as aggressiveness. Tolerating the Verbal and nonverbal behavior of individuals to follow their interests, to be firm on their stance, and to be certain of their justifications, feelings, and way of thinking without any hesitation is called assertiveness (Rezayat & Dehghan Nayeri, 2014). Assertiveness is the basis of, empowering nurses to become independent in nursing activities for appropriate decision-making.

For professional nurses, assertiveness is considered an essential hallmark for effective communication with colleagues, patients, and their families (Rezayat & Dehghan, 2014). The one who is using assertiveness appropriately in its true meaning is doing things in her/his interest without harming the dignity and respect of the other person. The one's self and aura are being maintained without violating someone else personal space. Assertiveness allows you to learn honesty, emotional stability, and self-directed enhancement. The body language changes and improves to a higher extent with the concept of

assertion. It allows the person to be more confident, and clearer in her/his aim, and objectives and reduces hesitation and self-pettiness.

METHODOLOGY

Walker and Avant identified three distinct processes in 2011 concept analysis, concept synthesis, and concept derivation (McEwen & Wills, 2014). It is the approach that nurses utilize the most because they can easily comprehend and describe the processes in detail. The Walker & Avant approach, which was first employed in 1986, will be used for the concept analysis of assertiveness. The concept analysis procedure, which entails the following steps, will analyze the concept of assertiveness:

The analysis process consists of the following steps:

1. Selecting a concept
2. Determining the purpose of the analysis
3. Identifying of all possible uses of the concept
4. Determining the defining characteristics/attributes
5. Modeling case identification with examples
6. Identifying related borderline, contrary, and model cases
7. Determining antecedents and consequences
8. Defining empirical referents

Selection of a Concept and Its Significance in Nursing

Assertiveness is of great importance in the nursing discipline. The basics of nursing profession depend upon the communication process, appropriate division of responsibilities, clarity of roles, and clear job description. The workload is being put on the shoulders of a person who is unaware of his/her clear job details and ways of saying no to seniors, colleagues, peers, and other healthcare team members. The increased workload on one person demotivates and increases anxiety levels. In later stages, the overburdened and pleasing junior who is unable to say no results in burnout and suffers through mental illness, disturbance, and ill health. Nurses are either thought to be kind people or required to exhibit behavior that matches other people's expectations and accommodates them. Nurses are burdened by other's workloads and are not able to refuse due lack of assertiveness. It is the utmost need of time that all nurses must be well aware of therapeutic communication and the appropriate use of assertiveness at appropriate times to avoid extra and unnecessary workload. Interacting with patients, colleagues, and other medical professionals is one of the many tasks that nurses must play. When nurses are equipped with strong communication skills and assertive behavior, these roles are enhanced and performed with greater effectiveness (Maheshwari, S., & Gill, K K). Mostly nurses show nonassertive behavior in their daily work routine and express low self-esteem because they are not trained for it. Self-esteem, confidence, and assertiveness are interrelated. Assertiveness is required for positive outcomes. The employees needed for the 21st century are highly self-esteem workers who make independent decisions, take risks, tenaciously pursue new ideas, and act on their own initiative (Garner, E 2012).

According to the study conducted by Maheshwari and Gill (2015), it was found that nonassertive nurses should receive assertiveness training or other similar strategies to improve their perception of themselves and their self-worth. Low self-esteem and passive attitude have been identified as key issues in the nursing profession. Nurses who exhibit strong assertiveness and have a high sense of self are more likely to provide therapeutic patient care (Maheshwari & Gill, 2015). Being assertive is highly important in patient care since nurses participate in decision-making and negotiation with patients, their

families, and other health providers. Assertiveness is required for good nurse/patient communication, and its development may also help the profession's confidence as it grows.

Purpose/Aim of the Analysis

Assertiveness is a necessary skill for today's nurses. As nurses move away from conventional subservient roles and perceived stereotypes, it is becoming increasingly clear that they must be assertive. The purpose of this concept analysis of assertiveness is to the concept in detail, so that it can be employed in the future. It will also provide a consistent definition to reduce ambiguity after identifying all the aspects of the concept. To clarify and deepen its significance, this paper will explore an analysis of the notion of assertiveness within the framework of nursing education and nursing practice.

The elucidation of the topic will allow the teachers to modify their teaching strategies and make them more effective and goal-oriented. According to Cabe and Timmins (2003), many nursing colleges in Ireland and the United Kingdom include assertiveness training in their curricula, there is no standard format for teaching assertiveness, nor are there fixed hours for content to be taught. To educate nursing students about importance of assertiveness to perform their responsibilities efficiently without taking unnecessary stress while working health care team. Nurse educators play a critical role in developing and implementing assertiveness training/education programmes for undergraduate nursing students. Because the nature of nursing employment requires a high degree of interpersonal and group contact, nurses regularly interact with other patients, colleagues, doctors, and other personnel. Furthermore, it helps nurses to understand the significance of assertive behavior and how they can improve their practices by using the assertive behaviors.

A lack of standardized assertiveness training in nursing education creates a significant challenge for preparing nurses for the complexities of modern healthcare. While assertiveness is increasingly recognized as crucial for nurses to effectively advocate for patients, collaborate with interprofessional teams, and manage the inherent stresses of their profession, inconsistencies exist in how this vital skill is taught. This absence of a clear, consistent approach in nursing curricula, despite its inclusion in some programs, leaves a gap in ensuring all nursing graduates possess the necessary assertiveness skills. This deficiency hinders nurses' ability to confidently navigate challenging interpersonal situations, potentially compromising patient safety, job satisfaction, and the overall quality of care (Ahyar & Oz, 2021). Therefore, a need exists to define and standardize assertiveness training within nursing education to equip future nurses with the tools they need to thrive in today's dynamic healthcare environment.

Definition of Assertiveness

The Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2002) defines "assertiveness is characterized by bold or confident statements and behavior". Assertiveness is a manner, skill and way of behaving. The quality of being confident and not to be frightened to say what you want or believe (Cambridge Dictionary, 2022). Assertiveness is defined in several ways. A variety of descriptions that don't quite convey the essence of assertiveness are included in the dictionary definitions of "assertiveness." Confident, straight forward, firm, positive, and insistent are among the words substitute of assertiveness. These are merely suggestions. None of these come close to what assertiveness is (Garner, E 2012). It can also be defined as, "Assertiveness involves appropriately expressing ideas, feelings, and boundaries while respecting other's rights, maintaining positive affect in the receiver, and considering potential consequences of the expression. It includes both positive and negative expressions and seeks to achieve personal and/or instrumental goals (Pfafman, 2020).

Identification of all Possible Uses of the Concept

The concept of assertiveness goes throughout the life span, on each step of life. The literature recommended that the concept of assertiveness can be used in health care as well as in other disciplines e.g. education, multinational companies, airlines, banks, and manufacturing companies. In health care, it can be used in clinical setups with the students, teachers, health care professional, patients, and their families. Moreover, it can be used in classroom teaching in education. The most important implication of the concept of assertiveness is when a subordinate works in different projects with senior authorities. The traditional node is placing extra burden and assignments on the shoulders of junior college and is being shifted by introducing the concepts of assertiveness in earlier education in all departments. Assertiveness is a critical characteristic for nurses without which real autonomy, professional status, or empowerment cannot be attained (Maheshwari & Gill, 2015). Assertiveness is the honest, caring, and lawful, manifestation of nurses. Assertiveness skills increase interpersonal relationships and decrease stress and tension among novice nurses and may aid in the development of care and a supportive attitude (Khanam et al., 2023).

Surrogate Terms

Assertiveness was first traced in the work of Ivan Pavlov. He explained it by defining the nervous system and its characteristics. Later in 1958, Wolpe was the first one who use the term assertiveness. The background of assertiveness is being cracked in the neurosciences and behavioral psychology domains. Interest in self-awareness, self-assertion, and the development of one's potential was growing in the 1960s (Peneva & Mavrodiev, 2013), The decade in which humanistic psychology first entered the historical scene. A self-assertion, self-actualization, and self-improvement aptitude assessment of the personality was started. The author claims that physiological factors dominated the reasons for stiffness and uncertainty (organic). Using I.P. Pavlov's ideas as a foundation (Peneva & Mavrodiev, 2013).

Clinical psychologists believed that non-assertiveness, or uncertainty, was a contributing factor in some mental illnesses, so to treat them, they instituted several training programs designed to promote assertiveness. The origins of assertiveness provide one trace to its meaning that assertiveness became popular in the late twentieth century as a result of movements such as Civil Rights in America, the women's movement, and the self-development movement. These were all nonviolent movements that succeeded in changing the rights of underprivileged groups. Beverley Hare, a writer, describes assertiveness as a journey. Her personal journey to assertiveness took her from low to high self-esteem, from dependence to interdependence, and from believing she was unattractive to knowing she was attractive. Her journey to assertiveness was both life-changing and life-enriching (Garner, E 2012).

Determination of the Defining Characteristics/Attributes

According to Walker & Avant, defining attributes are the symbols and revealed over time. Additionally, these attributes are considered as the focus of significance for concept analysis (Schiller, 2018). Recent research has attempted to provide a clear and content-based description of the concept and has identified three key characteristics of assertiveness: behavior, affection, and cognition, even though its distinguishing characteristics have been controversial for a considerable amount of time (Vagos & Pereira, 2010).

During the literature search, and review found some frequent content/attributes for assertiveness. These include self-esteem, comprehension with all correlated peers, seniors, and colleagues, clear identification of issues to be discussed, appropriate communication skills (verbal, non-verbal, and therapeutic) communication, confidence, and maintenance of eye contact. Some other important

attributes enlisted by theorists and psychologist are listening actively and responding in a non-threatening way to maintain self-efficacy and reliability (Peneva & Mavrodiev, 2013).

An assertive professional maintains eye contact while communicating with seniors, peers, and colleagues on any conflicting issue and expresses one's self clearly. Moreover, optimistic thinking, proactive dialogue development, ability to seek information and analyze situations, politeness, and humbleness are other defining characteristics of assertiveness. To be assertive, one should give due respect, importance, and regard to the other person. Assertiveness allows persons to communicate on being same level and make a mutual decision by collaboration, negotiations, and communication. Assertiveness is the best way to manage conflict... Conflict in the workplace is unavoidable, whether you're a supervisor or a coworker, either as part of your job position or as part of your relationships with others (Garner, E 2012).

Model, Borderline and Contrary Cases

Model Case

A model case explained all critical attributes of a concept (Walker & Avant, 2011). Nurse "A" was taking care of a patient with a head injury after a road traffic accident. The patient was under treatment by Dr. X. He was a renowned neurosurgeon and worked as head of department for the hospital. Dr X was popular for his anger and attitude. On the second day of admission, the nurse identified that the patient had a wound on his chest and he required an immediate orthopedic consultation with an x-ray. The nurse discussed the issue with the duty doctor and asked him to inform the physician. The doctor refused because of the reputation of the physician being arrogant. The nurse clearly stated the need for the patient's urgent review to the nurse manager and convinced the duty doctor to inform the physician about the case. The review of the patient was done and rib fractures were identified and treatment given. The process of smooth communication improves the environment of the ward and confidence among team members.

Borderline Case

A borderline case illustrates some of the critical attributes of the concept (Walker & Avant, 2011). Nurse "B" was on duty in the gynecological ward. She received a patient after a cesarean section. The patient remained Nil Per Oral (NPO) for almost 6-8 hours. Once oral was started nurse allowed the patient to take sips of water and green tea. During the room visit after half an hour, the nurse found the patient was drinking apple juice. The nurse asked the patient to take sips of green tea to avoid vomiting and nausea. The attendant of the patient proposed that apple juice is also a liquid and the doctor advised liquids for today. The nurse softly and smoothly explained the difference in fluid and identified the patient's desire to regain energy however if you like you can take juice but let me check with the physician. Later on, she consulted the physician to allow the patient liquids other than green tea and water. The physician allowed her to take juices and soup after one more hour. The issue was resolved and the patient remained comfortable.

Contrary Case

The contrary case contains none of the defining attributes of the concept (Schiller, 2018). Nurse C performed administrative roles in an A-class hospital. At the end of the shift, it was identified that the lights of the corridor were out of order. The assistant informed the nurse and asked her to initiate a demand so the light was in place. The nurse refused and asked to wait for the other day. At night, an old patient slipped as there was no light. The patient broke his hip joint and skull. He was placed on a ventilator and the hospital faced a huge amount of penalty in the form of cash.

Determination of Antecedents and Consequences

Walker and Avant define antecedents as occurrences that must be present or occur before the concept. Conversely, consequences are events that the concept may cause or result in. (Schiller, 2018).

Antecedents

There are mainly three components of antecedents of assertiveness. These include a conflict situation that has occurred, there is someone who has adhered him/herself to the situation, and the consequences /results when assertiveness is being implemented. The assertiveness may result in increased confidence in the person, ability to comprehend a situation, mutual understanding, ability to negotiate, and a cooperative relationship.

Increased motivation

One of the most important advantages of assertiveness is that it helps you eliminate the fear and stress that are still present in many of our life and work interactions, whether they are demanding seniors, angry patients, or non-cooperative coworkers. When nurse learns to behave assertively it raises their confidence, self-esteem, and motivation ultimately increasing work capacity and competency. High levels of self-esteem are linked with encouraging clinical competence and primarily influence patient nursing care (Maheshwari, S & Gill, K K 2015).

Improved patient satisfaction

The most important feature in the healthcare sector is Patient satisfaction. Assertiveness results in the professional development of nurses which in turn results in more patient satisfaction. The idea of assertiveness has been widely used in nursing writing and has been proven to be a crucial strategy for preventing negative events in healthcare and enhancing patient safety (Carlos & Ana, 2021). Assertiveness and emotional intelligence training programs can influence attitudes, emotions, and behaviors, allowing new psychiatric nurses to provide the best possible care to patients (Carlos & Ana, 2021).

Empirical Referent

Empirical indicators aid in identifying and quantifying the defining characteristics of the concept. (Schiller, 2018). As per the literature reviewed it is explored that there are reliable tools are available to assess assertiveness. The assessment also included Rosenberg's Global Self-Esteem Scale, The Rosenberg Global Self-Esteem Scale was used in Arabic. The scale was created to assess both worldwide negative and positive attitudes towards oneself. (Abed, et, al. 2015). The questionnaire includes 46 questions designed to gather data on verbal and nonverbal communication styles, anxiety and fear control, active orientation, work habits, questions about coworkers, and negotiating the system (Abed, et, al, 2015). Assertive Interpersonal Schema Questionnaire (AISQ) test for Assertiveness. The AISQ was created to evaluate the assertiveness-related domain of cognition, which can be thought of as a collection of fundamental assumptions about oneself, other people, and social situations or encounters.(Peneva & Mavrodiev, 2013).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

To sum up, it can be identified that assertiveness is a key component for development of smooth team work, identification of boundaries and delegation of duties. Assertive employees prevent the organization from upcoming, unseen loss and damage in form of money, resources and infrastructure (Taylor,et al., 2005).. Assertive professional is more productive, confident, resilient and optimistic. The overall reputation and production of organization in form of quality patient care can only be enhanced

by developing employee for assertiveness s(Kılıç, & Sevinç, 2018). Assertiveness is an essential social ability. It may take longer to resolve problems than forceful dominance or quiet submission. However, it is the path to the healthiest and satisfying human habits. The entreaty of assertiveness is that it can coexist peacefully with two opposite emotions, namely anger and dread.

In conclusion, assertiveness emerges as a cornerstone of effective nursing practice, fostering not only individual well-being but also contributing significantly to a positive and productive healthcare environment. As demonstrated, assertiveness facilitates smoother teamwork, clarifies professional boundaries, and empowers nurses to delegate tasks effectively, ultimately safeguarding organizations from potential losses and maximizing resource utilization (Taylor et al., 2005). Furthermore, assertive professionals exhibit increased productivity, confidence, resilience, and optimism, leading to enhanced patient care and a stronger organizational reputation (Kılıç & Sevinç, 2018). While cultivating assertiveness may require more time and effort than resorting to aggressive or passive behaviors, it represents the most sustainable and healthy approach to interpersonal interactions. Its unique ability to harmoniously integrate seemingly disparate emotions like anger and fear underscores its value as an essential social skill for nurses navigating the complexities of modern healthcare. Therefore, prioritizing the development of assertiveness in nursing education and practice is crucial for cultivating a competent, confident, and compassionate nursing workforce.

The findings of this concept analysis of assertiveness in nursing highlight its critical role in navigating the complexities of modern healthcare. The model case demonstrates how assertive communication, even in the face of hierarchical pressures, can ensure timely and appropriate patient care. The borderline case illustrates the nuanced application of assertiveness, balancing patient preferences with clinical needs through effective communication and collaboration with the physician. Conversely, the contrary case underscores the detrimental consequences of a lack of assertiveness, where inaction led to a significant adverse event. These examples reinforce the importance of assertiveness as a learned skill crucial for nurses to advocate for patients, collaborate effectively, and maintain a safe and efficient work environment.

Furthermore, the analysis of antecedents and consequences reveals the multifaceted impact of assertiveness. Antecedents, such as conflict situations and the nurse's commitment to resolving them, set the stage for assertive action. The consequences, including increased confidence, improved mutual understanding, and enhanced cooperative relationships, demonstrate the positive outcomes of assertive behavior. As noted, assertiveness contributes to increased motivation by reducing stress and fostering self-esteem, ultimately leading to improved work capacity (Maheshwari & Gill, 2015). Moreover, it plays a vital role in enhancing patient satisfaction by promoting professional development and ensuring safe, effective care (Carlos & Ana, 2021).

Finally, the existence of empirical referents, such as the Rosenberg Global Self-Esteem Scale and the Assertive Interpersonal Schema Questionnaire (AISQ) (Abed et al., 2015; Peneva & Mavrodiev, 2013), provides a means of measuring and quantifying assertiveness, allowing for targeted interventions and further research. By fostering assertiveness in nursing education and practice, healthcare organizations can cultivate a workforce equipped to meet the challenges of today's dynamic healthcare landscape, ultimately improving patient outcomes and promoting a positive work environment.

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